

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON SIMULATIONS AND LECTURES IN TEACHING PHILIPPINE POLITICS AND GOVERNANCE AMONG GRADE 11 STUDENTS AT DR. JOSE P. RIZAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

Paul Enrique C. Casas¹, Reynaldo F. Dinampo²,

¹ *Dr. Jose P. Rizal Senior High School, Santo Cristo, Dasmariñas City, Cavite Philippines*

² *Langkaan II National High School, Road 5, City Homes Resort Ville, Langkaan 2,
Dasmariñas City, Cavite Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

Rooted in a comparative approach, this study explores the impact of simulations and lectures on the performance of Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) learners at Dr. Jose P. Rizal Senior High School (DJPRSHS), a stand-alone public Senior High School in Cavite, Philippines. It examines how these two teaching methods influence student understanding of a specific unit in Philippine Politics and Governance, a subject under the HUMSS strand. Using multiple-choice pretests and posttests, it compares student performance in simulations—through questions on procedural aspects of the three branches of government (e.g., budget process, legislation, judicial review)—and in lectures—through questions measuring factual recall and conceptual understanding. Employing a quasi-experimental one-group pretest post-test design, the study assesses the relative effectiveness of both methods. Statistical analysis revealed a significant difference in student performance between the two methods, with lectures exhibiting a slightly larger effect size, but simulations showing marginally higher mean differences. Both methods yielded positive learning outcomes, though further investigation is needed to explore potential integrative effects between them. Beyond the statistical results, the study acknowledges pedagogical reflections drawn from praxis and reflective practice, particularly the value of simulations in fostering experiential learning and critical thinking. In closing, the researchers note that while simulations and lectures serve distinct

instructional purposes, their combined use may contribute to more meaningful learning experiences.

Keywords: *Simulation, Lecture, Philippine Politics and Governance, Comparative Study, Praxis, Social Studies Education.*

INTRODUCTION

Choosing effective teaching methodologies is critical for educators as they directly influence learner (i.e. student) outcomes and the integrity of the subject matter (Killen & O'Toole, 2023). Indeed, teachers are expected to balance content and pedagogy to ensure effective lesson delivery. Given the pivotal role educators played in shaping student success, Burroughs et al. (2019) emphasized that teachers were among the most influential factors in determining students' future outcomes. Dinampo, Barrameda, and Bunan (2024), all seasoned school leaders, highlighted the importance of aligning teaching methods with content to create a cohesive learning experience in subjects (i.e. courses) like philosophy. Indeed, as educational contexts shifted, many teachers explored innovative approaches to meet the diverse needs of learners.

Simulation-based learning, known for its potential to deepen the active and experiential learning among learners, is also well-known with teachers looking for appropriate and modern teaching strategy (Chernikova et al., 2020). When the Philippine Department of Education adapted the 2C-21-R pedagogical framework in 2019, they effectively espoused a policy anchored on learner centered, competency-based and outcomes-focused approaches among basic education institutions in the country. 2C-21-R stands for 2C – Constructivist and Contextualized, 2I – Inquiry-based and Interdisciplinary, R-Reflective. These pedagogical principles highlight student engagement and reflective learning as hallmarks of education.

According to Mahon et al. (2021), educational praxis is an instructional approach that is self-consciously moral, political, reflective, and informed, with the goal of promoting social and educational change. The study is aligned with the broader objectives of this educational praxis, it is the driving force of this research project. One important aspect of which is geared to the nurturing of the praxis development of learners, aiming to improve their capacity towards active participation through self-discovery and active learning.

Reflective practice is another key starting point of this study. For Mertler (2024), this refers to the process of critically assessing and analyzing strategies and processes especially in the context of action research. While this study is not action research per se, the researchers see reflective practice as one of the *raison d'être* of the project, and within the context of education, this has a direct impact on student outcomes. Mertler is a known figure in action research, focusing specifically on reflective practice and systematic inquiry. As such, it is also the goal of this study to improve pedagogical practice among teachers not just among researchers but the immediate institution where they are

connected. This goal is beyond merely attaining theoretical knowledge or contributing to academic discipline.

In line with the primary variable of this research, studies show that simulation offers the potential to increase engagement and long term-retention (Baranowski & Weir, 2015; Clark & Scherpereel, 2024), while lectures, another variable, provide immediate knowledge gains (Wunische, 2019), ideal in practical settings. This study thus, in terms of contributing to the discipline, examines how well role-playing simulations are utilized specially when teaching dynamic topics such the budget process, legislation, and judicial review. Considering that, according to Clark & Scherpereel (2024), simulations are not always that effective compared with lectures in promoting factual knowledge and similar curricular content.

Simulations, being a constructivist strategy, are centered on active learning instead of the passive receipt of information in more traditional methods. In their discussion of the benefits of student-designed simulations in relation relations education, Maertens at Cheli (2023) agrees with Pacala (2021) that learners become more effective when students build on existing knowledge. This was further supported by Clark & Scherpereel (2024) and Baranowski & Weir (2015), who sought to prove that simulations increase critical thinking and learner engagement. In line with this, this research has explored how simulation-based learning contributes to greater understanding of the material.

Effective teaching strategies, according to Killen and O'Toole (2023), are structured methods designed to cater to a wide range of student needs. Abulhul (2021) and Paolini (2015) argue that teaching strategies and methods are interchangeable, but both aim to improve learning outcomes. They support the need for a balance between teacher-centered and learner-centered strategies to enhance performance. As previously discussed, reflective practice appears to be crucial to successful teaching (Mahon et al., 2021).

Killen and O'Toole (2023) further stressed the importance of educators modifying their approaches considering critical introspection. Crowley (2021) examined the significance of self-awareness in pedagogy, suggesting that personal traits like introversion influenced teaching styles. This concept aligns with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), which mandated that teachers assess their own professional practices. In this context, the researchers argue that teachers have the autonomy to select appropriate pedagogies matching their comfort levels, as well as the needs of the learners. This is another avenue where reflective practice becomes crucial.

Going back to the context of praxis, DuPlass (2021) argued that civic education plays a vital role in social studies, not only transmitting knowledge but shaping learners' identities. Reyes (2019) also emphasized the importance of teacher-student relationships, particularly regarding how teaching strategies impacted Philippine politics students. Additionally, Wongmahesak et al. (2025) supported the use of active learning techniques, such as debates and simulations, to improve political science instruction, which was increasingly integrated into the Senior High School curriculum in the

Philippines. Khanh (2024) also advocated for the gradual introduction of interactive teaching techniques.

In terms of lectures, it is indeed one of the oldest teaching strategies, aiming to transfer knowledge from teacher to learner in the most practical manner. For Broadwell (1980), lectures are a conventional approach that can successfully transmit information, particularly when accompanied by visual aids to improve understanding. As such, for (Bailey et al. (2022), students still place a high value on lectures, especially when they are interesting and relevant, even in the age of interactive learning. Although lectures might not be appropriate for every learning style, they are still a useful tool for imparting foundational knowledge and structured content (Wunische, 2019; Toomey et al., 2020).

However, modern adaptations of lectures have now emerged to make them more interactive. Dustkobilovich and Laylo (2020) emphasized the effectiveness of the lecture-dialogue format, where teachers present content through questions that encourage active student participation. This transforms the lecture into a more engaging experience. In contrast, the straight lecture, as defined by Broadwell (1980), relies solely on the instructor's delivery and does not incorporate student interaction, making it a more passive form of learning. Furthermore, it is this lecture, the lecture-dialogue, they fall back on, when practically is needed, while study wanting to establish sufficient teacher-learner engagement.

At this juncture, teachers, including the researchers involved in this study, are particularly concerned with how these ideas interact and are applied in the classroom. The Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) program is a strand in the academic track of the Senior High School curriculum in the Philippines that aims to prepare learners for careers in governance, psychology, and sociology, among others (Department of Education, 2016). This strand combines traditional academic learning with practical skills, with Philippine Politics and Governance (PPG) serving as one of its specialized subjects that focuses on the country's political systems and government.

For Dinampo, Barrameda, and Bunan (2024), the goals of the Senior High School program can only be achieved by using 2C-2I-R pedagogies more conscientiously. Simulation-based learning may help improve critical thinking and practical problem-solving skills in this regard (Kolb, 1984; Harper, 2018; Khanh, 2024). Furthermore, it enhances student involvement by connecting theory and practice. While lectures, especially in the context of lecture-dialogues, offer a more stable and time-tested alternative (Dustkobilovich and Laylo, 2020).

Accordingly, two teacher-researchers at Dr. Jose P. Rizal Senior High School (DJPRSHS), a stand-alone public Senior High School in Cavite province, Philippines, set out to improve learning outcomes for Grade 11 HUMSS learners through a comparative study of teaching methods. Inspired by a student's suggestion to debate topics related to the three branches of government—a unit in PPG—one of the two teacher-researchers (implementing researcher) applied simulation-based activities in his classes. This

approach allowed for a comparison between simulations and traditional instructional strategies, assessing their impact on student engagement and understanding.

The implementing researcher believed that, while debates present opposing viewpoints (Pedroso & Magno, 2024) and may provide an intellectual exercise for learners, simulations offer a more dynamic, role-based learning experience that aligns with constructivist methods and is likely to improve students' practical understanding of governance (Pedroso & Magno, 2024; Schnurr & MacLeod, 2021). Furthermore, simulations provide an experience similar to debates while also covering the concepts and practices in PPG through active learning and role-playing (Schnurr & MacLeod, 2021). It should be emphasized that the decision to use simulations was driven not only by the teacher's professional discretion and instructional idiosyncrasy but also by careful consideration of learner needs. This choice reflects the teacher's autonomy in selecting appropriate methodologies while ensuring alignment with student learning requirements.

Additionally, it was made with the intent to examine the method's effectiveness relative to other instructional strategies. This move is consistent with PPST and the assertions of Mahon et al. (2021) and Killen & O'Toole (2023)

The second teacher-researcher, a master teacher and school leader, served as mentor and supervisor to the first teacher-researcher, guiding the latter into a structured comparative research initiative. This mentorship helped establish methodological consistency and promote a collaborative research environment. The partnership between supervisor and subordinate aligns with the assertions of Coimbra et al. (2020) on the importance of democratic and collaborative research practices, as recommended in their study on teacher development dynamics in Brazil.

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of two teaching methods—simulation and lecture—through a comparative analysis of learner performance in Grade 11 PPG classes at DJPRSHS, a stand-alone public Senior High School in Cavite Province, Philippines. The study examines how these instructional strategies impact learner outcomes, particularly in relation to their pretest and posttest scores as comparative measures of performance.

Specifically, the study addressed the following research questions:

1. What is the performance of learners in the simulation method based on their pretest and posttest scores?
2. What is the performance of learners in the lecture method based on their pretest and posttest scores?
3. Is there a significant difference in learner performance across different sections (i.e., classes) using the simulation method?
4. Is there a significant difference in learner performance across different sections using the lecture method?

5. Is there a significant comparative difference in overall posttest performance between learners using the simulation and lecture methods?

Rooted in the principles of praxis and reflective practice, which provide practical grounding for this comparative study (Mahon et al., 2021; Mertler, 2024), the researchers view teachers and learners as the primary beneficiaries. However, the opportunity to contribute to the field of social studies education cannot be discounted. In this regard, apart from a Conclusion, a Reflection component was integrated into the Results and Discussion to highlight the pedagogical insights gained from the comparative approach, replacing a traditional acknowledgment section while maintaining the formal structure of research.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental comparative research design, utilizing a one-group pretest post-test approach to evaluate learners' performance before and after instructional interventions (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). To ensure comparability, all learners experienced both lecture and simulation-based methods. The sample consisted of all Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) learners at DJPRSHS in Dasmariñas City, Philippines, totaling 107 learners.

Data was collected using pretests and post-tests created by one of the teacher-researchers who was actively teaching the subject. These tests assessed learners' recall, comprehension, and analytical progress; for the purposes of this study, "academic performance" or "performance" refers to the results of these assessments, which were administered at the beginning and end of the unit.

The comparative analysis of the two instructional methods was structured as follows:

Simulation-based learning was measured using a 20-item multiple-choice set focused on processes related to the three branches of government, including but not limited to the State of the Nation Address, legislative process, and the role of the judiciary.

Lecture-based learning was assessed using a separate 20-item multiple-choice set, covering knowledge-based questions on topics such as the powers, roles, and responsibilities of the President, Congress, and the Judiciary.

The lecture method was carefully implemented to maintain separation from simulation-based content, although the potential for cross-effects was acknowledged. Measures such as separate assessments and structured segmentation of learning sessions were put in place to minimize overlap (Toomey et al., 2020; Siegel-Stechler & Gee, 2023). In this study, cross-effect refers to the combined impact of both instructional methods on learner performance.

Pretests were administered from September 30 to October 2, 2024, while actual simulation activities and lecture-dialogues were conducted alternately from October 2 to November 13, 2024. Learners engaged in simulated activities, including: (a) The State of the Nation Address (analogous to the U.S. State of the Union Address); (b) Presidential appointments and their review by the Commission on Appointments (similar to U.S. Senate confirmation hearings); (c) The budget process and deliberations; (d) The law-making process and bicameral conference committees; (e) Presidential approval, veto of laws, and veto overrides; and (f) Judicial review.

Meanwhile, lecture-dialogues covered non-simulated content, such as: (a) roles, powers, and responsibilities of the Executive; (b) Legislative; and (c) Judicial branches of government.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Results and Discussion presents the study's findings, which are analyzed to address the previously discussed research objectives. The emphasis is on learner performance through two teaching methods: simulation and traditional lecture. The results provide information about the effectiveness of each method, both overall and within specific sections of the subject.

Key topics covered include overall performance with the simulation method (Table 1), overall performance with the lecture method (Table 2), breakdowns by section for each method (Tables 3 and 4), a direct comparison of the two methods (Table 5), and an overall comparison of post-test means (Table 6). The findings are discussed in relation to the previously presented research objectives.

1. What is the performance of learners in the simulation method based on their pretest and post-test scores?

Table 1: Level of Performance in Simulation Method

Level in Simulation	Pre-Test		Post Test	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Very High	1	1	39	36
High	22	21	48	45
Low	76	71	20	19
Very Low	8	7	0	0
Total	107	100	107	100

Following the simulation intervention, Table 1 demonstrates a significant improvement in learner performance. In the pre-test, only 21% of learners received high scores, compared to 71% who received poor scores. Post-test results, however, showed a notable change: low performers fell to 19%, whereas 45% attained a high level and

36% a very high level. This illustrates how knowledge and interest in PPG can be raised through simulation-based learning.

These results are in line with studies by Clark and Scherpereel (2024) and Baranowski and Weir (2015), which highlight the potential of simulations to promote critical thinking, bridge theory and practice, and improve practical skills like public speaking and leadership. Wongmahesak et al. (2025) claim that the results further validate constructivist approaches because simulations enhance learners' understanding by enabling them to apply abstract ideas to actual situations. The results demonstrate that simulations are well worth the investment, especially for dynamic issues like government, even though they require a substantial amount of resources (Wunische, 2019).

2. What is the performance of learners in the lecture method based on their pretest and post-test scores?

Table 2: Level of Performance in Lecture Method

Level in Lecture	Pre-Test		Post Test	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Very High	0	0	10	9
High	21	20	80	75
Low	74	69	17	16
Very low	12	11	0	0
Total	107	100	107	100

Table 2 shows a similar positive shift in learner performance after the lecture intervention. Pre-test results showed that 69% of learners had low scores, but post-test results showed that 75% of the learners had high scores and 9% had very high scores, while low performers had fallen to 16%. This suggests that interactive elements, like the lecture-dialogue format (Dustkobilovich & Laylo, 2020), can enhance engagement and knowledge transmission, which runs counter to the claim that lectures are only passive (Broadwell, 1980).

These results align with those of Bialek et al. (2022), who stress the significance of delivering lectures effectively. Simulations foster practical understanding while lectures are excellent at imparting fundamental knowledge, highlighting the benefits of a hybrid approach (Toomey et al., 2020; Siegel-Stechler & Gee, 2023). In keeping with the study's focus on reflective practice and praxis development, future research could examine this synergy to enhance teaching methodologies in PPG (Mahon et al., 2021).

3. Is there a significant difference in learner performance across different sections using the simulation method?

Table 3: Contingency Table of Section-Wise Simulation Performance

Sections	Mean Pre	Mean Post	Mean Difference	Computed T	Tabular Value (0.05)	Significance
HUMSS 11-A	8.51	14.11	-5.60	-16.47	2.04	Significant in favor of Post Test
HUMSS 11-B	8.38	12.56	-4.18	-11.61	2.04	Significant in favor of Post Test
HUMSS 11-C	9.18	14.18	-5.00	-19.23	2.02	Significant in favor of Post Test

Table 3 shows significant post-test score improvements in all three HUMSS sections (A, B, and C) after the simulation intervention. The mean score for HUMSS 11-A, for instance, rose from 8.51 on the pre-test to 14.11 on the post-test, with a highly significant computed t-value of -16.47 and a mean difference of -5.60. HUMSS 11-B (mean difference: -4.18, t-value: -11.61) and HUMSS 11-C (mean difference: -5.00, t-value: -19.23) showed comparable gains. These results show how well simulations work to increase learners' comprehension of topics in PPG.

The results are in line with studies by Clark and Scherpereel (2024) and Baranowski and Weir (2015), which highlight how simulations can promote critical thinking, bridge theory and practice, and develop useful skills like public speaking and leadership. Because simulations allow learners to apply theoretical concepts to real-world scenarios, the results also support constructivist approaches (Wongmahesak et al., 2025).

4. Is there a significant difference in student performance across different sections using the lecture method?

Table 4: Contingency Table of Section-Wise Lecture Performance

Sections	Mean Pre	Mean Post	Mean Difference	Computed T	Tabular Value (0.05)	Significance
HUMSS 11-A	7.83	12.77	-4.94	-22.45	2.04	Significant in favor of Post Test
HUMSS 11-B	8.32	11.44	-3.12	-14.86	2.04	Significant in favor of Post Test
HUMSS 11-C	8.58	13.97	-5.39	-44.92	2.02	Significant in favor of Post Test

Table 4 reveals significant improvements in post-test scores across all three HUMSS sections following the intervention of the lecture. For instance, the mean score for HUMSS 11-A went from 7.83 on the pre-test to 12.77 on the post-test, with a highly significant computed t-value of -22.45 and a mean difference of -4.94. HUMSS 11-B (mean difference: -3.12, t-value: -14.86) and HUMSS 11-C (mean difference: -5.39, t-value: -44.92) showed comparable gains. These findings show how well lectures work to improve students' comprehension of PPG.

The results support Broadwell's (1980) claim that lectures are a useful tool for imparting knowledge, especially when they are given in an interesting way (el Bialy et al., 2022). The teacher's preference on the use of lecture-dialogue, likely introduced notable enhancements that went beyond passive delivery by introducing interactive components (Dustkobilovich & Laylo, 2020). It should be noted though that it does not include simulations but merely focused on back-and-forth discussions with the learners.

5. Is there a significant comparative difference in overall post-test performance between learners using the simulation and lecture methods?

Table 5: Contingency Table of Differences: Simulation vs. Lecture Methods

Method	Mean Pre	Mean Post	Mean Difference	Computed T	Tabular Value (0.05)	Significance	Effect Size
Simulation	8.71	13.64	-4.93	-44.82	1.98	Significant in favor of Post-4.33 Test	
Lecture	8.25	12.78	-4.53	-64.71	1.98	Significant in favor of Post-6.26 Test	

The comparative efficacy of lecture and simulation techniques is presented in Table 5. Both instructional approaches resulted in statistically significant improvements in learner performance. The mean difference for simulations was -4.93 (pre-test: 8.71; post-test: 13.64), while the mean difference for lectures was -4.53 (pre-test: 8.25; post-test: 12.78). This indicates that although both methods were effective, simulations yielded a slightly higher raw score improvement compared to lectures.

While lectures remain an essential tool for imparting fundamental knowledge, particularly when interactive components are integrated, simulations appear to be more effective in fostering active learning, skill development, and the practical application of theoretical concepts (Baranowski & Weir, 2015; Clark & Scherpereel, 2024). One possible reason why lectures still performed well in comparison to simulations is the implementing teacher's use of lecture-dialogues, a more interactive form of lecture that incorporates student-centered discussions (Dustkobilovich & Laylo, 2020).

Effect size values (i.e., Cohen's *d*) for both methods indicate large and meaningful differences in academic performance. The effect size for simulations was -4.33, while for lectures it was -6.26. These substantial effect sizes suggest that both instructional methods had a significant impact on learner outcomes (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). From a statistical perspective, the lecture method exhibited a slightly stronger effect size, suggesting a more consistent overall impact on performance. However, simulations produced a slightly greater mean difference, indicating a small but notable edge in raw score improvement.

From a praxis and reflective practice perspective, simulations remain valuable as they promote experiential learning, active engagement, and deeper conceptual understanding beyond test performance. While lectures provide a structured approach to content mastery, simulations offer an immersive learning experience that enhances critical thinking and real-world application, making them particularly effective in bridging theory with practice.

Additionally, the possibility of cross-effects (see Methodology) cannot be entirely dismissed, despite efforts to separate the application of both instructional methods. Measures such as separate assessments and clear segmentation of learning sessions were implemented to minimize overlap. However, as suggested in previous studies, the integrative effect of using both methods within the same learning experience may have influenced overall student performance (Toomey et al., 2020; Siegel-Stechler & Gee, 2023).

Conclusions

The primary objective of this study was to examine the impact of simulation-based and lecture-based instructional methods on the academic performance of Grade 11 learners taking PPG at DJPRSHS. The study analyzed the effectiveness of these instructional strategies by comparing learners' pre-test and posttest scores.

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1. Inferential analysis showed that there was significant progress in the performance of learners using simulation-based strategies based on their posttest scores (pre-test: 8.71; posttest: 13.64). This suggests that simulations enhance critical thinking, practical application and active engagement.
2. The data also revealed that there is a noticeable increase in the performance of learners in the lecture-based components of the unit (pre-test: 8.25; posttest: 12.78), which reinforces its effectiveness in promoting foundational knowledge while also helping in recall of key concepts, especially when combined with more interactive elements, like lecture-dialogues.
3. The three sections under HUMSS 11 under this study consistently demonstrated significant increase in posttest scores in the simulation components. This shows the effectiveness of the teaching method in increasing experiential learning, regardless of the sectioning of the learners.

4. Results also revealed that lecture component of the study has similarly contributed to the increase in performance among the three sections of HUMSS 11 learners proving its capability to promote theoretical and conceptual learning.

5. In statistical terms, although both the lecture and simulation components significantly improved academic performance, the lecture approach exhibited a slightly larger effect size compared to simulations (effect size for lecture: -6.26, for simulation: -4.33), suggesting a somewhat stronger overall impact. However, simulations yielded a greater mean difference, highlighting their potential for fostering more active and engaging learning experiences. From the perspective of praxis and reflective practice, simulations create opportunities for deeper engagement by providing a more dynamic and immersive learning environment. While lectures remain a well-established and effective method for reinforcing conceptual knowledge, simulations encourage experiential learning and critical thinking that extend beyond test performance.

The study supports the Alternative Hypothesis (H_1), indicating a statistically significant difference in academic performance between learners exposed to simulation and lecture methods, with simulations showing slightly better outcomes, though both approaches produced positive learning gains. The differences observed between simulation and lecture methods underscore the importance of aligning instructional strategies with specific lesson objectives and learning goals. A balanced integration of both methods could enhance the overall learning experience, strengthening both theoretical understanding and practical application.

It should be noted, however, that at a 0.05 level of significance, there remains a possibility that the observed differences were influenced by random variation or cross-effects between the two methods. This suggests the need for further investigation to better categorize their individual impacts.

Recommendations

Based on the results and discussion, as well as data analysis, the following recommendations are offered:

For Teachers: To improve learner engagement as well as increase their academic performance, teachers are encouraged to use and improve on the use simulations strategies in teaching social studies. Simulations offer the opportunity to improve the teaching of civic education related topics as well as those that involve practical application and critical thinking. Efforts could also be made to improve the effectiveness of lecture-based instruction by integrating it with more interactive elements.

For School Leaders: The researchers also see the need to encourage school administrators to promote and support simulation-based strategies by advocating for the provision of materials that would support model congress type of activities by such as appropriate conference rooms, gavel and mallet, maces, among others. It will also be important for administrators to provide opportunities for professional development for

teachers to ensure greater success in the implementation simulation and other experiential learning activities.

For the Department of Education: Aside from extending efforts in the provision of materials for model congress type of activities. The Department of Education should consider establishing instructional leadership roles to oversee the adoption of innovative teaching strategies in social studies classrooms. Additionally, to improve instructional effectiveness and align with competency-based frameworks like the 2C-2I-R model, teachers should be given practical training on active learning strategies.

For Future Researchers: Without discounting the current value of this study for reflective practice and praxis development, future studies could further explore more robust research designs including experimental and longitudinal studies to explore the effectiveness of simulation techniques and other active learning strategies not just in social studies, but in other subject areas. Because of the inherent limitations of ne-group pretest-posttest design, the researchers also recommend the use of “pretest-posttest design with a double pretest” (Bell, 2012, cited in Reimer, Love, Wölfer, & Hewstone, 2021), especially if time and practically of such is permissible in the context of other researchers.

For Broader Application: To maximize learning outcomes in social studies education, further research could explore blended approaches by combining lecture and simulation methods (Toomey et al., 2020; Siegel-Stechler & Gee, 2023).

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the study, ethical standards were strictly followed, ensuring that participants’ rights and well-being were safeguarded. To protect respondents’ privacy, data confidentiality was rigorously maintained. Their names were not associated with their responses, and all information was handled following the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173, 2012). Participants were assured that all responses would be used exclusively for research and academic purposes and that their data would be securely stored and protected.

Participation was regarded as part of the teaching-learning process. However, respondents were given the option to request exclusion from data analysis if they felt the need. Finally, the study was conducted without conflict of interest, ensuring that all findings were interpreted impartially and objectively. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all research results were used for scholarly inquiry, academic reflection, and praxis improvement.

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